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Xist activates DFFA and DFFB.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We describe here activation of cell death effectors DFFA and DFFB by Xist following transgenic Xist ncRNA expression in human cells.